

Interpretable Campus Mobility Pattern Discovery via Non-Negative Matrix Factorization

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Abstract—Efficient management of mobility infrastructure requires moving beyond time-series analysis to uncover latent structures in traffic dynamics. While urban-scale networks have been extensively studied, high-density microcosms such as university campuses remain largely under-explored despite their critical role in city-wide mobility. This paper presents an unsupervised learning framework for decomposing large-scale spatio-temporal traffic data collected at the perimeter of the Bordeaux University campus. Using Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) on a multi-year dataset from nine bi-directional sensors, we isolate four physically meaningful latent traffic patterns. Unlike conventional dimensionality reduction techniques, NMF’s non-negativity constraint ensures a parts-based representation that respects the additive nature of traffic, enabling the direct mapping of latent factors to specific mobility regimes: daily commuting cycles, city-based through-traffic, and transient flows driven by external congestion spillovers. A comparative analysis of campaigns from 2022 and 2024 reveals high structural stability (mean reproducibility score of 0.98), confirming these patterns as invariant functional motifs. However, the data also reveals a shift toward a non-linear, anticipatory routing regime in 2024, empirically linked to metropolitan ring-road saturation. Notably, our results demonstrate that the campus functions as an inadvertent relief corridor for surrounding urban congestion, exposing structural vulnerabilities in local road infrastructure. By framing campus mobility as an unsupervised pattern recognition problem, this work provides a scalable diagnostic framework for identifying the functional roles of the network nodes and quantifying the impact of exogenous perturbations on localized infrastructure.

Index Terms—Interpretable AI, Non-negative Matrix Factorization, Mobility Pattern Discovery, Intelligent Transportation Systems, Smart Campus, Spatio-temporal Traffic Analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

The efficient management and optimization of mobility infrastructure is strongly dependent on our ability to analyse and interpret large continuous data streams generated by Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) [1]. These systems, deploying technologies such as loop detectors, pneumatic tubes, Radar and Lidar sensors, and cameras [2], produce large quantities of mobility data that capture complex underlying states and dynamic patterns such as morning / evening rush-hour commuting, mid-day deliveries, night-time logistics, weekend recreational movements, etc. Traditional methods based on physical laws and statistical inference are typically constrained to isolated intersections, specific arterial segments, or localized network topologies [3]. However, within large-scale urban road

networks, spatio-temporal traffic data exhibit highly dynamic and multidimensional characteristics, creating significant challenges for the extraction of fundamental mobility patterns [4]. A key challenge, therefore, is to move beyond descriptive time-series analysis and uncover the latent components that govern observed traffic dynamics.

Most existing studies focus on city-scale transportation networks. In contrast, high-density local environments such as university campuses remain comparatively under-explored. Yet campuses function as microcosms of urban mobility, combining residential, educational, and service-related activities within a constrained spatial perimeter [5]. The campus boundary thus acts as a critical interface between internal activity and the surrounding urban network. Understanding mobility at this interface requires distinguishing between endogenous flows (originating or terminating within the campus) and exogenous flows that traverse it [6]. This raises a central question: *can perimeter traffic measurements alone reveal the functional role of a campus within the broader urban system, and disentangle internal demand from externally induced traffic?*

From a pattern recognition perspective, this problem can be framed as the discovery of latent structure in multivariate spatio-temporal signals. Rather than focusing on short-term prediction, this work adopts an unsupervised approach to identify stable and physically interpretable traffic patterns embedded in observed data. To this end, we employ Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NMF), which decomposes traffic time series into a set of non-negative spatial basis patterns and associated temporal activations [7]. This formulation is particularly well suited to traffic analysis [4], as it respects the non-negative nature of flow measurements and yields a parts-based representation in which observed traffic can be interpreted as an additive combination of a finite number of latent mobility regimes [8]. Compared to alternative methods such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) or Vector Quantization (VQ), NMF provides improved interpretability by avoiding non-physical negative components and allowing multiple patterns to be active simultaneously [7].

While standard unsupervised learning algorithms (e.g., k-means clustering) are frequently used for pattern discovery, they are fundamentally limited in this context as they enforce a ‘hard’ assignment, where each sensor is mapped to a

single cluster. This is inconsistent with the physical reality of traffic networks, where observed volumes at a single node are typically a superposition of multiple independent mobility modes. Furthermore, clustering identifies groups of similar observations but offers limited insight into the underlying constituent patterns or their relative contributions. By contrast, NMF performs a soft decomposition that isolates the specific temporal signatures and spatial supports of each mode, allowing for a more nuanced and physically grounded interpretation of the network’s functional states [9].

Originally introduced for applications such as image analysis and semantic topic modelling [7], NMF has been successfully applied to transportation systems to extract spatio-temporal traffic patterns and support long-term analysis [10], [11]. Its extension to tensor-based formulations have further improved its ability to capture time-evolving dynamics [12]. Prior work has demonstrated its effectiveness in identifying localized and interpretable structures in traffic data, including congestion patterns, seasonal variations, and shared mobility usage [13], [14]. However, these studies primarily focus on large-scale urban networks or predictive tasks, leaving the mesoscopic scale of campus environments largely unexplored, particularly from a functional and diagnostic perspective.

In this paper, we investigate the extent to which perimeter traffic alone can reveal the internal and external dynamics of a campus mobility system. Using data collected from nine strategically positioned sensors at the main access points of Bordeaux University Campus, we show that traffic dynamics can be consistently represented using a small number of latent patterns. These patterns correspond to distinct mobility regimes, including commuting flows, through-traffic, and short duration events induced by external congestion. Notably, our analysis reveals that the Bordeaux University Campus’ road infrastructure does not solely cater to internal mobility demand, but also operates as an unintended relief corridor for surrounding urban congestion, exposing a dependency on external traffic conditions.

The main contributions of this paper are threefold. First, we formulate campus perimeter mobility analysis as an unsupervised pattern discovery problem, enabling the separation of endogenous and exogenous traffic flows. Second, we propose an NMF-based decomposition framework that extracts a compact set of interpretable latent patterns and associates them with functional roles of access points, including through-traffic-dominated, exchange-dominated, and event-driven behaviour. Third, we demonstrate that these patterns are temporally stable and spatially consistent across datasets collected in 2022 and 2024, highlighting their relevance for descriptive mobility analysis and infrastructure diagnostics.

II. METHOD

This section describes the proposed pattern recognition framework for campus mobility analysis. The methodology follows three main steps : (i) data construction, in which raw sensor measurements are aggregated into structured spatio-temporal matrices, (ii) latent feature extraction via unsuper-

vised learning, and (iii) cross-dataset comparison to evaluate the stability and functional interpretation of the extracted components. Although the factorization algorithm is classical, the contribution lies in its structured application to perimeter traffic data and in the interpretation of the resulting components as stable and physically meaningful mobility regimes.

Fig. 1. Map showing the spatial distribution of sensors around the Bordeaux University Campus. The campus perimeter is highlighted with hashed shading. Campus sensors are referred to as C_m and external sensors as E_n . Note : all C_m are bidirectional.

Bordeaux University’s campus, spanning 187 hectares, is one of the largest university campuses in Europe, accommodating around 58,000 students and employees [15]. Located within Bordeaux Metropolitan area (44.799829° N 0.615535° W), mainly across the municipalities of Pessac, Talence and Gradignan, the campus occupies a strategic position at the interface of residential, commercial, industrial, and administrative zones. This location induces strong coupling between campus-related traffic and city-scale through-traffic, resulting in mobility patterns that reflect both internal demand and external flows. Consequently, campus roads are subject not only to recurrent commuting flows but also to persistent non-campus related traffic, especially during peak periods.

From a pattern recognition perspective, the campus perimeter can be viewed as a multivariate observation system in which each access point serves as a spatial channel and traffic counts represent coupled temporal signals. To capture these dynamics, two measurement campaigns of two weeks each were conducted at nine entry and exit points in October 2022 and February 2024. This dual-dataset design enables the evaluation of temporal robustness and reproducibility of the extracted patterns. Figure 1 illustrates the spatial distribution of the traffic sensors C_m deployed around the campus perimeter (hashed area), and the permanent sensors operated by Bordeaux Metropolis, denoted by E_n . Here, C_5 and C_6 represent primary gateways capturing predominantly endogenous flow. Meanwhile, corridors C_3 – C_4 and C_2 – C_7 – C_8 serve as the network backbones, facilitating the bulk of through-traffic and acting as the primary interfaces for mobility pattern propagation across the site.

A. Data pre-processing

All C_m are bi-directional. The raw dataset consists of time-stamped vehicle detections recorded at each sensor. Vehicles were initially categorized as passenger cars, heavy vehicles (buses and trucks), and bicycles. Preliminary analysis indicated that motorized traffic accounted for nearly 95-98% of the total observed traffic at each sensor, with passenger cars representing the primary modal share. On this basis, all vehicle categories are aggregated into a single composite flow variable, ensuring a simplified and robust representation of total traffic intensity. Note that this study focuses exclusively on road-based traffic and, therefore, does not consider pedestrian and public-transport-related flows.

Data pre-processing was designed to construct a representation of the traffic time-series signals suitable for unsupervised pattern discovery. To this end, traffic counts were aggregated into 15-minute intervals. Such temporal windows, typically between 10 and 60 minutes, are used to achieve a balance between temporal granularity and statistical stability [16]. Notably, within each aggregation window, the median traffic count was utilized instead of the arithmetic mean. This choice serves as a robust estimator to mitigate the influence of outliers, such as sensor measurement artefacts or transient vehicle clusters, thereby preserving the underlying rhythmic structure of the network. The finalized datasets for both the 2022 and 2024 campaigns exhibited 0% missing values, ensuring a continuous and synchronized time-series across all sensor nodes without the need for heuristic imputation.

The pre-processed data are organised into a non-negative matrices in the form $\mathbf{V} = [V_{t,l}] \in \mathbf{R}_+^{T \times L}$, where $V_{t,l}$ denotes the median traffic count at sensor l during time interval t . This matrix representation formalizes the dataset as a multivariate spatio-temporal signal, where each column L corresponds to a directional traffic channel (i.e., one direction of a bi-directional sensor), and each row T represents a temporal observation. To focus on recurrent mobility structures and exclude nocturnal noise, our analysis is restricted to weekday data between 06:00 and 20:00. The temporal dimension is constructed by stacking all 15-minute intervals across the observation period, such that $T = N_{days} \times N_{bins}$, where $N_{bins} = 56$. Two separate matrices are constructed for respective measurement campaigns: $\mathbf{V}_{2022} \in \mathbf{R}_+^{T_1 \times L_1}$ and $\mathbf{V}_{2024} \in \mathbf{R}_+^{T_2 \times L_2}$. This dual representation enables direct comparison of latent structures across time and supports the assessment of pattern stability.

B. Non-negative Matrix Factorization

To extract interpretable mobility signatures from the stacked sensor data, we employ Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NMF). NMF is an unsupervised learning technique that decomposes the high-dimensional observation matrix \mathbf{V} into two low-rank non-negative matrices [7], $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbf{R}_+^{T \times \kappa}$ (temporal activations) and $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbf{R}_+^{\kappa \times L}$ (the spatial basis or sensor weights), such that

$$\mathbf{V} \approx \mathbf{W}_{T \times \kappa} \mathbf{H}_{\kappa \times L} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2. Frobenius reconstruction error of Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) as a function of κ for two traffic datasets for 2022 (blue line) and 2024 (red line).

Here, κ denotes the factorization rank. The non-negativity constraint is central to our framework; unlike Principal Component Analysis (PCA), it ensures that components represent purely additive physical processes, directly aligning with the additive nature of traffic flows and enhancing the physical interpretability of the results. The factorization is obtained by minimizing the Frobenius norm of the reconstruction error:

$$\min_{\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{H} \geq 0} \|\mathbf{V} - \mathbf{W}\mathbf{H}\|_F^2 = \sum_{t,l} \left(V_{t,l} - \sum_{k=1}^{\kappa} W_{t,k} H_{k,l} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

To ensure the reliability of the factorization and avoid convergence toward local minima, we adopt a consensus NMF framework. We utilise Non-negative Double Singular Value Decomposition (NNDSVD) [17] for initialization, providing a deterministic starting point that improves convergence over random initialization.

Model selection and sensitivity analysis were conducted by performing $n = 20$ independent NMF runs for each rank $\kappa \in \{2, 3, \dots, 10\}$. For each rank, a consensus matrix K was constructed, where each entry $K_{i,j}$ represents the probability that two spatial channels i and j are associated with the same latent component across all runs, to evaluate the stability of sensor groupings. As shown in Fig. 2, the Frobenius reconstruction error exhibits a clear "elbow" at $\kappa = 4$, after which error reduction becomes marginal.

The stability of this rank is quantitatively substantiated by a Cophenetic correlation coefficient of 1.0 (Fig. 3). The resulting consensus matrix is strictly binary, demonstrating that the spatial clusters are perfectly stable and invariant to initialization noise [9]. While the spatial structure suggests three primary sensor communities, a rank of $\kappa = 4$ was retained to isolate a fourth independent temporal activation pattern. This specific rank captures the "route-transfer" dynamics without inducing "pattern splitting," where primary functional signatures fragment into non-interpretable noise. This approach provides a mathematically rigorous and physically consistent basis for the subsequent spatio-temporal analysis.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 4 presents the temporal activation profiles of the latent components extracted by Non-negative Matrix Factor-

Fig. 3. Consensus matrix for campus sensors for $\kappa = 4$. The matrix represents the probability that any two sensors are assigned to the same latent mobility pattern across 20 independent NMF runs with NNDSVD initialization. The lack of intermediate values demonstrates that the factorization is invariant to random initialization. Note that E and X refer to the campus entry and exit directions.

Fig. 4. The 4 temporal patterns for 2022 (blue line with circles) and 2024 (orange line with squares), with their intensity normalized by the norm.

ization (NMF) for the nine perimeter posts C_m . Profiles from 2022 (blue, circles) and 2024 (orange, squares) campaigns are superimposed for comparison. To ensure scale-invariance across datasets, each component is normalized by its Euclidean (L_2) norm, denoted as $|W_k| = \sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^n W_{t,k}^2}$. The overlap between the signatures suggests a high degree of temporal stability in the underlying traffic patterns. This invariance is quantitatively validated through cross-year alignment using the Hungarian matching algorithm [18]. We utilized cosine similarity as the cost metric to prioritize the alignment of temporal shapes over absolute magnitudes. The procedure yielded a mean matched similarity of 0.948, with individual patterns ranging from 0.905 ($\kappa = 1$) to 0.987 ($\kappa = 4$). This consistently high correlation across all components confirms that the latent traffic modes are not artifacts of a specific campaign but represent stable, reproducible signatures of the

Fig. 5. The percentage contribution of the 4 patterns for 2022 (blue bars) and 2024 (orange bars) for campus measurements posts C_m . Note that E and X refer to the campus entry and exit directions.

network dynamics.

Pattern 3 ($\kappa = 3$) exhibits highest L_2 norm in both datasets, identifying it as the dominant latent traffic mode. Between 2022 and 2024, the component energy $|W_k|$ increased 22% for $\kappa = 3$ and 14.5% for $\kappa = 4$, while decreasing by 8% and 30% for $\kappa = 1$ and 2, respectively. These shifts reflect fluctuations in the relative intensity of each mobility regime rather than structural changes of the temporal signatures. Indeed, temporal profiles for $\kappa = 2, 3, 4$ remain highly congruent across campaigns, suggesting that the NMF-extracted components represent intrinsic, recurrent mobility processes rather than transient phenomena. This structural stability aligns with longitudinal studies of [19] on the reproducibility of macroscopic traffic states.

Figure 5 illustrates the spatial basis vectors (relative sensor weights) for the 4 temporal patterns. The spatial distributions remain largely invariant across both measurement campaigns, reinforcing the interpretation that each sensor maintains a stable functional role within the network. While the global spatial structure is preserved, localized deviations in specific sensors are observed; these anomalies are examined in the subsequent sensitivity analysis.

A. Campus commute traffic ($\kappa = 2, 4$)

Figure 4 reveals a distinct temporal complementarity between $\kappa = 2$ and $\kappa = 4$, suggesting that these components encode the bidirectional daily campus commuting cycle. Pattern $\kappa = 2$ is characterized by a pronounced morning peak (07:30-09:30) and a secondary midday surge (13:30-14:00), with no evening activity. In contrast, $\kappa = 4$ exhibits a dominant evening peak (16:30-18:45) and a midday exit peak (12:00-12:45), with minimal morning activity. This temporal opposition identifies $\kappa = 2$ as predominantly inbound (entry) traffic and $\kappa = 4$ as outbound (exit) traffic. These profiles are consistent with established observations of mobility behaviour in university environments, where entry and exit flows align with the start and end times of academic / professional activities [20]. From a pattern recognition perspective, NMF effectively disentan-

Fig. 6. Time variation of the normalized medians traffic between 06:00 and 20:00 for external sensors E_{10} and E_{11} , and the campus sensor C_6 for 2022 (blue) and 2024 (orange) campaigns. Each external sensor corresponds to a distinct traffic direction.

gles these directional mobility behaviours which are typically superimposed in aggregated traffic signals, an interpretation supported by the high cross-year stability (cosine similarity of 0.953 for $\kappa = 2$ and 0.948 for $\kappa = 4$).

The commuting interpretation is spatially validated by the basis weights in Fig.5. At gate C_6 , the primary campus gate designed to restrict through-traffic, the signal is almost entirely reconstructed by these two components, indicating a high functional specialization. Similarly at C_5 , a secondary access point, these patterns account for 50-60% of the signal energy across both campaigns. This spatial concentration provides direct empirical evidence that these components isolate campus exchange flows, as further evidenced by the median traffic-count time series (Fig. 6). As noted by [21], such signatures are most reliably isolated at locations where exchange movements are minimally confounded by through-traffic. Consequently, the localized nature of C_5 and C_6 provides the high signal-to-noise ratio necessary for NMF to recover the intrinsic rhythmic structure of campus mobility.

This interpretation is reinforced by contrasting these results with external sensors E_{10} and E_{11} (Fig. 6). Unlike the campus gates, these sensors exhibit flat temporal profiles characteristic of generic urban traffic [22], confirming that the NMF decomposition specifically captures localized campus dynamics.

A comparison of the campaigns reveals a systematic temporal shift. The morning activation of $\kappa = 2$ in 2024 is delayed by 15–30 minutes relative to 2022. In contrast, the evening activation ($\kappa = 4$) remains largely invariant. This asymmetry suggests that morning commutes are more sensitive to exogenous factors, such as the late-autumn timing and reduced daylight of the 2024 campaign, while evening departures remain relatively inelastic [23], [24]. Notably, NMF’s ability to recover structurally identical components despite these localized temporal shifts highlights its utility in separating stable behavioural archetypes from seasonal perturbations.

Beyond the primary gateways, $\kappa = 2$ and $\kappa = 4$ exhibit

TABLE I
PEARSON CORRELATION BETWEEN EXTERNAL BOUNDARY SENSOR TRAFFIC AND NMF TEMPORAL PATTERN ACTIVATIONS (κ) FOR 2022 AND 2024 DATASETS

Sensor	Pattern (κ)	Correlation (2022)	Correlation (2024)
E6	$\kappa = 1$	-0.25	-0.31
E6	$\kappa = 2$	-0.11	-0.08
E6	$\kappa = 3$	0.48	-0.52
E6	$\kappa = 4$	0.65	-0.33
E7	$\kappa = 1$	-0.08	-0.05
E7	$\kappa = 2$	0.05	0.30
E7	$\kappa = 3$	0.49	0.63
E7	$\kappa = 4$	0.45	0.49
E8	$\kappa = 1$	-0.13	0.29
E8	$\kappa = 2$	0.02	0.05
E8	$\kappa = 3$	0.52	0.62
E8	$\kappa = 4$	0.55	0.71
E9	$\kappa = 1$	-0.24	-0.36
E9	$\kappa = 2$	-0.26	-0.16
E9	$\kappa = 3$	0.71	0.72
E9	$\kappa = 4$	0.57	0.67

significant contributions at posts C_1 , C_8 , and C_9 . A comparative analysis reveals that while the spatial weights for $\kappa = 4$ remain remarkably stable across campaigns, $\kappa = 2$ shows a relative decline in 2024. This divergence suggests that morning inbound patterns ($\kappa = 2$) are more susceptible to network-level reconfiguration and changes in gateway preference, whereas evening exit flows ($\kappa = 4$). This behavioural asymmetry is examined in greater detail in section III-D.

B. City through-traffic ($\kappa = 3$)

The temporal profile of $\kappa = 3$ is characterized by sustained intra-day activity with significantly lower diurnal variation compared to the commute-related patterns ($\kappa = 2, 4$). After approximately 10:00, the activation profile maintains a stable plateau, consistent with urban traffic regime [22]. While the 2024 profile exhibits a steeper early-morning activation gradient compared to the gradual increase observed in 2022, the midday and afternoon dynamics remain invariant. This suggests that $\kappa = 3$ represents a through-traffic component that is largely decoupled from university-specific academic schedules.

The spatial support for $\kappa = 3$ (Fig. 5) supports this interpretation. High weights are concentrated at sensors C_2 , C_4 , and C_7 in the inbound direction, and at C_2 , C_3 , and C_8 in the outbound direction. These nodes define two principal corridors (C_7 – C_2 and C_4 – C_3) aligned with *Cours de la Libération*, a major artery carrying traffic to and from the ring road. To quantitatively validate this interpretation, external sensors E_6 , E_7 , E_8 and E_9 located along *Cours de la Libération*, in proximity of C_2 and C_3 are used as an exogenous reference. Note that E_6 facilitates inbound traffic, E_7 and E_8 captures outbound flow, and E_9 a mixture of both.

Pearson correlation analysis (Table I) reveals that $\kappa = 3$ maintains a stable and dominant association with external

boundary-layer flows, with coefficients ranging 0.48 to 0.72 in absolute value. These values consistently exceed those of campus-specific patterns ($\kappa = 1,2$), with sensor E_9 showing the strongest sustained alignment ($r > 0.70$). While $\kappa = 4$ also exhibits high correlation with external sensors, this is largely a by-product of temporal synchronization between campus departures and the broader metropolitan evening rush. The distinct signature of $\kappa = 3$ remains its sustained intraday plateau, a feature absent in the commuting regimes.

To account for potential phase shifts and directional disparities, similarity was further evaluated using normalized Dynamic Time Warping (NDTW) [25]. Consistently low NDTW distances for sensor E_9 (54.0 in 2022 and 58.5 in 2024) confirm a strong structural alignment with $\kappa = 3$ across both campaigns.

Conversely, a significant structural divergence was observed at sensor E_6 , where the NDTW distance rose from 87.9 to 271.7. This anomaly is explained by a radical shift in the network’s physical state: in 2022, E_6 operated at approximately one-third of its 2024 volume with non saturation, likely due to localized flow suppression from undocumented roadworks. In 2024, volumes tripled and the sensor reached a state of persistent saturation (77% of intervals). This transition into a “choked” flow regime flattens the traffic signal, effectively decoupling the sensor’s output from the latent urban rhythms and explaining the observed shift toward negative correlation. Despite this localized volatility at E_6 , the stability of NDTW distances across the remaining external sensors corroborates the role of $\kappa = 3$ as a robust, invariant representation of urban transit.

A significant advantage of the NMF framework in this context is its capacity for source separation at multi-functional nodes. Sensors such as C_2 , C_3 and C_8 exhibit raw signals where campus exchange and city through-traffic are confounded. The NMF decomposition effectively “de-noises” these signals by partitioning the variance into distinct, additive components: the stable city-wide background is isolated in $\kappa = 3$, while the rhythmic commuting surges are recovered in $\kappa = 2,4$. This disentanglement confirms that the extracted components represent the underlying functional logic of the network rather than simple spatial aggregates..

Overall, the combination of (i) weak diurnal variability, (ii) spatial alignment with arterial corridors, and (iii) consistent association with directional external traffic provides compelling evidence that $\kappa = 3$ identifies the dominant through-traffic component in the network. This isolation allows for the quantification of exogenous traffic pressure on campus infrastructure, independent of internal academic demand.

C. Route transfer traffic ($\kappa = 1$)

Pattern $\kappa = 1$ exhibits distinct characteristics compared to both commuting and through-traffic components, specifically regarding its high temporal variability and spatial localization. Unlike other patterns, $\kappa = 1$ shows substantial inter-year fluctuations in activation intensity and temporal structure, suggesting a sensitivity to transient network conditions rather

Fig. 7. Lagged cross-correlation between ring-road congestion and $\kappa = 1$ activation for 2022 and 2024 campaigns. Positive lag values indicate congestion leading route-transfer activation.

than recurrent behavioural cycles. This relative instability is quantitatively reflected with the lowest individual reproducibility score at 0.905 (cosine similarity). Spatially, this component is primarily supported by posts C_1 , C_2 and C_3 for inbound traffic and C_4 and C_7 for outbound flow. While the core contributing posts are consistent, notable inter-year deviations occur at C_7 (entry) as well as C_2 and C_8 (exit), reflecting shifts in preferred bypass routes.

The temporal evolution of $\kappa = 1$ is characterized by multi-modal activity peaks during morning, afternoon, and evening periods. However, the timing and magnitude of these activations lack the cross-campaign stability observed in $\kappa = 2,3,4$. Notably, the 2024 profile exhibits a sharp morning peak (07:15-07:45) contributing to a 40% increase in the component’s L_2 norm relative to the previous campaign. Similarly, the 2022 profile shows a pronounced midday (13:00-13:45) and late-evening (after 18:30) surge. These discrepancies confirm that $\kappa = 1$ does not encode a stable diurnal rhythm but instead most probably captures condition-dependent mobility responses to external network stress.

To quantify the relationship between campus diversion and external pressure, we performed lagged cross-correlation and Granger causality analyses (Fig. 7) against traffic data from the Bordeaux Ring Road (E_1 , E_2 , E_3 and E_4). The statistical evidence reveals a sharp transition in coupling dynamics between campaigns. In 2022, ring road saturation was relatively sparse, occurring in only 9 of the 24 15-minute intervals during the morning and evening rush hours (Fig. 8). Under these conditions, $\kappa = 1$ exhibited a structured, delayed response to highway congestion, with cross-correlation peaking at lags 6–7 ($r \approx 0.35$), corresponding to a 30-35 minute delay. Granger causality tests confirm this predictive relationship ($p < 0.05$ starting at lag 4), with a peak influence at lag 6 (F-stat ≈ 19.2 , $p \approx 7.1 \times 10^{-18}$). This validates a reactive re-routing mechanism where drivers enter the campus network only after congestion has matured on the primary highway.

In 2024, ring road saturation increased significantly, reach-

Fig. 8. Time variation of the median congestion on the ring road between exit 16 serving the campus and exit 15 further west. The left plot presents data for the outer ring road and the right plot for the inner ring road. Congestion is estimated as the ratio of the measured vehicle flow to the total theoretical lane capacity. If this value is greater than 0.9, the situation is over-saturated characterised by frequent slowdown, stop and go conditions [26].

ing 22 out of the 24 15-minute intervals. This heightened stress coincides with a breakdown of the stable lag structure. Cross-correlation coefficients remained weak ($r \approx -0.20$), and Granger causality became non-significant at the previously dominant intermediate lags ($p > 0.05$ for lags 1-4). This suggests a shift toward a non-linear or anticipatory routing regime. As previously noted, E_6 transitioned from a free-flow state in 2022 to being saturated in 77% of monitored intervals. Simultaneously, C_2 exhibited persistent saturation during morning rush-hours, effectively limiting the reactive intake. This surge coincided with the arrival of a travelling community (*gens du voyage*), who entered the campus perimeter via axe E_6 - C_2 .

This localized "choking" of the network provides a physical basis for the loss of linear temporal coupling in the NMF activations. The intensity increase in $\kappa = 1$ was driven by a constant external pressure rather than the rhythmic, transient congestion fluctuations observed in 2022. Consequently, the campus transitioned from a reactive bypass (where surges followed ring-road delays) to a saturated bottleneck, where the diversion is constant and no longer statistically lagged against the ring road's state.

The transition from a structured 35-minute lag in 2022 to a decoupled, high-intensity state in 2024 provides empirical evidence of the campus network's structural vulnerability. By functioning as an unintended relief corridor, the campus infrastructure is forced to absorb the overflow of a saturated metropolitan arterial system, subjecting internal roads to high-intensity traffic surges that are entirely exogenous to university activity.

D. Inter-year behavioural variability

The high structural stability evidenced by the cross-year alignment, yielding a mean matched similarity of 0.948, confirms that the inferred mobility modes represent an invariant functional backbone of the network. This reproducibility provides a robust framework for assessing how the spatial importance of these modes evolves over time. A comparative analysis reveals that inter-year variability is primarily expressed through localized shifts in the spatial distribution of pattern weights rather than transformations in the underlying functional definitions of the traffic states. While the core

roles associated with each component remain consistent, their relative importance at individual posts evolves, indicating adaptive route-choice behaviour within a stable overall demand structure.

At the network scale, a persistent spatial specialisation is observed. Gateways C_5 , C_6 , and C_8 (inbound) and C_1 , C_5 , C_6 and C_8 (outbound) maintain their primary role of serving campus-commute traffic ($\kappa = 2,4$), while C_4 and C_7 (inbound) and C_3 (outbound) remain dedicated to through-traffic ($\kappa = 3$). Furthermore, the recurring dominance of the route-transfer component ($\kappa = 1$) at C_1 and C_2 (inbound) identifies them as structurally significant "relief valves" for the surrounding urban grid.

Superimposed on this stable structure, localized reconfigurations are observed at specific posts. At C_6 (outbound), the campus-commute component's contribution increased by 20 percentage points in 2024, reaching near-total dominance. This indicates a reinforcement of functional specialisation. Conversely, at C_5 (inbound), a decrease in commuting weights is offset by a rise in route-transfer ($\kappa = 1$) activity. This indicates a competition for limited physical capacity between flow types; as external bypass demand increases, it effectively displaces a portion of the traditional commuting flow at that specific entry point.

Between the two campaigns, several posts underwent functional transitions. C_1 (inbound) shifted from campus-commute to route-transfer dominance, while C_2 (outbound) transitioned from commuting to through-traffic. Similarly, C_7 (outbound) moved toward route-transfer dominance, reflecting a strategic shift in how drivers utilize the campus perimeter under varying external network stress.

These observations align with adaptive route-choice mechanisms, whereby drivers selectively reallocate paths in response to evolving congestion patterns [27]. Overall, the analysis indicates that while the network's global functional architecture is remarkably stable, consistent with the theory of invariant urban motifs [28], individual campus access points operate within a dynamic equilibrium. Their fundamental roles persist over time, but their relative utilization adapts to the shifting constraints of the surrounding urban environment [11].

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper demonstrates the effectiveness of Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) as an unsupervised and interpretable framework for disentangling complex spatio-temporal traffic dynamics at the perimeter of a large university campus. As high-density "micro-cities," urban campuses present a unique challenge where internal academic rhythms intersect with metropolitan transit. Developing a comprehensive Intelligent Transportation System (ITS) to monitor these flows is critical for operational resilience; however, establishing a permanent hardware-based observatory with synchronized sensors at every gateway is costly. To this end, our study provides a computationally efficient alternative, leveraging NMF to decompose aggregate traffic counts into four latent

components ($\kappa = 1,2,3,4$) that represent the functional backbone of the network.

A comparative analysis of the 2022 and 2024 campaigns reveals a robust dynamic equilibrium. While the fundamental functional components remained structurally invariant (yielding a matched similarity of 0.948), their spatial utilization at specific access points adapted to external network constraints. Commuting patterns ($\kappa = 1,2$) exhibited high structural rigidity at dedicated gateways, whereas the through-traffic component ($\kappa = 3$) consistently isolated the dominant through-fare urban flow, effectively de-noising campus-specific signatures from arterial transit corridors.

The route-transfer component ($\kappa = 1$) proved to be a highly sensitive diagnostic tool for detecting external perturbations. By integrating lagged cross-correlation and Granger causality analyses, we demonstrated a transition from a linear, reactive diversion regime in 2022 to a more complex, non-linear regime in 2024. This evolution was empirically linked to localized over-saturation and transient events, proving that unsupervised learning models can successfully isolate "transient motifs" from "recurrent cycles", a core requirement for developing resilient smart city infrastructure.

In summary, this research advances the application of AI models in urban planning by providing a compact, interpretable representation of mobility dynamics without the need for ubiquitous and expensive hardware deployments. The proposed framework serves as a scalable diagnostic tool for identifying node-level functional transitions and network-level sensitivity to exogenous stress. Future work will focus on the real-time integration of these latent components into predictive ITS architectures, aiming to enhance the autonomy and resilience of the Bordeaux campus environment against both recurrent congestion and stochastic perturbations.

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